

Modulated predictive controllers (**M²PC**) with novel geometric approach.
Reduced computational burden with zero steady-state tracking error and satisfactory dynamic behavior.
SyRel motor drive application.

Case Study: SyRel Drive Model

Considering the **model-based nature** of the proposed **M²PC**, the following assumptions are made. **1) Accurate representation of the SyRel flux maps, 2) dq reference frame.**

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{i}_{dq} = \mathbf{L}^{-1} [\mathbf{v}_{dq} - R_s \mathbf{i}_{dq} - \mathbf{Q} \omega_r \boldsymbol{\psi}_{dq}]$$

Simulation Results

Current control at **low modulation index**, $ma < 0.5$ (speed of 500 rpm).
Performance comparison with standard **M²PC**.

Results: Comparable dynamic and steady-state performance.

Current control at **low modulation index**, $ma > 0.8$ (speed of 1500 rpm).

Results: Worse dynamic performance and same steady-state performance.

Modulated Model-Predictive Control

The main idea of classical **M²PC** formulations is to find a feasible solution of duty cycles among each pair of voltage vectors calculated using an **evaluation function**.

- 1) **Classical M²PC** find a solution among the **eight possible switching states**.
- 2) The **proposed M²PC** evaluates **three out of eight possible switching states**.

Evaluation Function $g(j) = \begin{bmatrix} g_d \\ g_q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (i_d^* - i_d^{k+1}(j)) + w_d I_d \\ (i_q^* - i_q^{k+1}(j)) + w_q I_q \end{bmatrix}$

Integral error terms

$$I_d = T_s (i_d^* - i_d^k) + \sum_{\ell=1}^{n-1} (i_d^* - i_d^{k-\ell})$$

$$I_q = T_s (i_q^* - i_q^k) + \sum_{\ell=1}^{n-1} (i_q^* - i_q^{k-\ell})$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} d_1 \\ d_2 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{G}_{dq} \begin{bmatrix} t_d - g_d(v_{0d}) \\ t_q - g_q(v_{0q}) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d_1 &\geq 0 \\ d_2 &\geq 0 \\ d_1 + d_2 &\leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2	\vec{v}_2, \vec{v}_3	\vec{v}_3, \vec{v}_4	\vec{v}_4, \vec{v}_5	\vec{v}_5, \vec{v}_6	\vec{v}_6, \vec{v}_1
Sec1	Sec2	Sec3	Sec4	Sec5	Sec6
$d_1 > 0$	$d_1 > 0$	$d_1 > 0$	$d_1 < 0$	$d_1 < 0$	$d_1 < 0$
$d_2 > 0$	$d_2 < 0$	$d_2 < 0$	$d_2 < 0$	$d_2 > 0$	$d_2 > 0$

$$\bar{t}_d = 2g_d(v_{0d}) - t_d$$

$$\bar{t}_q = 2g_q(v_{0q}) - t_q$$

The **Classical M²PC** identifies the feasible sector to refer the duty cycle calculation in both linear and overmodulation operation. The **resulting duty cycles are positive**.

The **proposed M²PC** refers the duty cycle calculation to one sector arbitrarily chosen. The **resulting duty cycles are positive and negative**.

Experimental Validation

Current control tracking at low modulation index.

Current control tracking at high modulation index.

Conclusions

The deterioration of the transient performance at a higher modulation index is the trade-off for having a **computationally more efficient M²PC algorithm** (i.e., more than 50 % less computations).